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Petroleum Industry Act 2021 and the Prospects of Enhanced Socio-Economic Development of Host Communities of Oil Producing Areas in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study intensively explored the prospective attributes of the petroleum industry act of 2021. It examined the inherent objectives of the new petroleum regulation as it pertains to addressing the socio-economic development of host communities of petroleum and natural gas (crude oil) producing and processing companies in Nigeria. The background to this study impressed that it has been a historical practice by humans living in any geographically defined society to exploit, produce and allocate collectively owned natural resources among the people. Also, the background to this study specifically informed that in any heterogenous society, agitations to have preferential consideration characterise the sharing and allocation of resources among units are inevitable. Hence, the study acknowledged that the exhibition of such tendencies in the course of sharing national revenue earnings is typical of the Nigerian situation. The study however identified that in the case of Nigeria, the various communities where crude petroleum and natural gas are explored, produced and processed in large commercial quantity continuously lament the high extent of degradation of their physical environments. Regrettably though, there has been a seemingly high level of lack of adequate compensations to these oil producing communities in terms of an appreciable level of socio-economic development. The study observed that the high rate of unemployment, poverty, hunger, infrastructural deterioration, etc. that characterise the socio-economic status of oil-producing communities does not justify the much revenue that is being consistently generated from these communities. The study used the secondary source as a method of data collection. With the instruments of journals, newspaper publications, as well as materials from the internet, the study reviewed literature on the challenges and prospects of the PIA 2021 as it relates to the administration of socio-economic development of host communities of oil companies in Nigeria. The study concluded by impressing that with the elimination of administrative corruption and the re-enhancement and consolidation of trust between the management of oil companies and their host communities, the objectives of the PIA for the socio-economic emancipation of oil-producing communities would be actualised.

Keywords: Administration, Government, Oil Companies, Oil-Producing Communities and Society.

INTRODUCTION

Historically, it is an unarguable fact that humans exist and survive in a particular geographical specification by exploiting, exploring, harnessing and distributing the natural deposits of resources. Even in the post-Hobbesian age, communal and social approach to the ownership of natural resources characterised the sharing of a society's commonwealth. This era entailed the vesting of the right and lawful obligation to distribute society's resources in an individual or body of individuals who exercise such functions on behalf of the society. Interestingly, this approach has continued to be characteristic of experiences in modern times.

Also, naturally, in any heterogenous society, there exists, agitations by the diverse individuals that make up such a heterogenous entity to register some degree of sentiment over the sharing formular adopted by any established constituted authority, overseeing the affairs of the particular region affected. Hence, there would always be the agitation for preferences in the pattern of distributing resources among the various units. In this regard, a firm and uncompromising demand by regions who contribute more in the collectively-owned resources for larger portion in the distribution process usually characterise the co-existential status of such a union. This system typically defines the federal system of government. Thus, federation entails the composition of a union by divergent geographically defined societies. In the Nigerian context, since crude oil exploitation and exploration constitutes the major source of revenue earnings for the country, the revenue sharing formula invariably captures the derivation principle. The derivation principle summarily necessitates the allocation of a special percentage for communities from where crude oil is exploited. Aside earmarking a special percentage for oil producing states in the revenue sharing formular, there are legislations and laws which provides for additional compensations for the host communities of oil producing areas in terms of socio-economic and infrastructural development benefits. Hence, the activities of crude oil exploration most times, inflict environmental degradation of affected communities.

One of the very significant objectives of the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) of 2021, is the provision in chapter 3 of the PIA Act which provides for the establishment of the host community development trust fund. The introduction of this scheme was primarily aimed at comprehensively addressing the existing socio-economic challenges that confront host communities in oil producing zones in Nigeria. This comes on the heels of the long years of abandonment or passive commitment to ameliorating the plight of communities whose ecological attributes have been polluted and degraded by the activities of oil exploration and exploitation by both indigenou s and foreign s companies. And so, the PIA among other things, aims as making sure that the terms of the Corporate Socia Responsibility (CSR) are seriously and transparently adhered to by oil companies. As a consequence, the PIA mandates oil companies to contribute 3% of their annual operational expenses to the socio-economic development of their host communities. This is also against the backdrop of the knowledge of the enormous revenue from the oil industry, including petroleum and natural gas. Hence, the revenue accruing from crude oil sales, royalties and taxes account for 75% of Nigeria's revenue earnings. Again, the sale of oil and natural gas accounts for 95% of Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings. Also, with over 37 billion barrels worth of yet-to-be exploited oil reserve, Nigeria is ranked 10th globally (Akinkugbe, 2024; Open Society Initiative for West Africa, 2014). Therefore, this study fundamentally focuses on determining the potential gains and prospects of the Petroleum Industry Act 2021, with regards to enhancing the socio-economic growth and development of host communities of oil producing communities in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the review research design. The research was guided by a resort to scientific investigations carried out by the researchers through the obtainment of data from several documented literature on articles, posts, writeups journal publications or articles relating to petroleum industry Act, oil producing communities and the socio-economic conditions of host communities of areas where petroleum

and natural gas are deposited, exploited and produced in large commercial quantities. The various data generated were interpreted and analysed using the deductive qualitative content analysis method.

Conceptual Clarifications

Petroleum Industry Act, 2021

Originally, in September 2020, former Nigerian President, Muhammadu Buhari transmitted a new bill in the Nigerian oil and gas industry to the National Assembly. The bill, then referred to as the Petroleum Industry Bill was sent to the both Houses of the National Assembly, comprising the Senate and the House of Representatives for a detailed study and possible approval. Consequently, after several months of diligent and comprehensive scrutiny, on the 1st of July 2021, the senate successfully passed the bill. The underlying reason for the slight delay was to give room for meticulousness and diligence in the examination of the proposed bill. Hence, the then Senate President, Ahmed Lawan was quoted to have said that the National Assembly would not be stampeded into “sacrificing thoroughness at the altar of speed”. Finally, on the 16th of August, 2021, the former President Buhari signed the bill into law. Henceforth, the Petroleum Industry Bill became known and referred to as the Petroleum Industry Act (Agbarakwe & Bredino, 2024).

Accordingly, the Petroleum Industry Act of 2021, is potentially designed to introduce workable reforms, regulations and strategies, fundamentally purposed at strengthening the operational capacity of the petroleum industry. Essentially, the promulgation of the new petroleum industry law has as one of its cardinal objectives, the introduction of strategic reforms in the operation of the national oil company, the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). As a consequence, the latter became known as the Nigeria National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL). Thus, the primary motive behind this is to make the NNPCL, self-reliant, self-regulatory and profit oriented. Among the very potent underlying reasons for the establishment of the PIA is the institutionalised bargain for the amount of money or royalties that oil companies should be giving to host communities. The negotiation started with the proposal by host communities for 10% of production earnings by oil companies. While the House of Representatives debated on a proposal between 2.5% to 5%, the senate finally pegged it at 3%. Also, the new petroleum act (PIA 2021), establishes a framework for enacting and enforcing aspects of statutory rules, meant to be binding and regulatory on oil companies and their mode of operations. Hence, these rules are fundamentally purposed at establishing new dispute resolution mechanisms with regards to issues pertaining to environmental cleanups of affected host communities as well as effecting some level of control and limitations to the extent of environmental pollutions, occasioned by the operational activities of oil companies (Thomas, 2021).

The PIA 2021 is also poised to holistically address the habitual incompetence, inefficiencies, official corruption and overall redundancy in the operational capacity of NNPC. Over the years, there has been a noticeably high level of poor budget performances in the activities of the NNPC- a situation occasioned by obvious administrative lapses. The existence of bureaucratic corruption in the NNPC has always led to administrative infractions and dubiousness with regards to the award of licences for the allocation of oil blocks, the allocation of licences for exploration, exploitation and production of crude oil, allocation of slots to independent marketers in the downstream for the lifting of refined petroleum products, as well as in everything that pertains to the issuance of contracts to private individuals or corporate entities. Regrettably, these perceived administrative lapses and deliberate infractions in the operational activities of the NNPC have often times, led to cases of poor remittances to the federation account. Also, the impact of bureaucratic corruption in the activities of the NNPC has always been known to have implication for rampant smuggling and illicit diversion of petroleum products to neighbouring countries. The immediate consequence of this is usually manifest in perennial situation of scarcity of petroleum products. On the whole, since petroleum constitutes Nigeria’s economic mainstay, a redundant or inefficient NNPC is bound to negatively impact socio-economic development of host communities of oil producing regions in particular and the Nigerian state at large. Therefore, the administrative rebranding of the NNPC under the

Petroleum Industry Act is critical to the attainment of the objectives of improving the socio-economic development imperatives of host communities of oil producing regions in Nigeria (Adat & Okpara, 2023).

Socio-Economic Development

A background establishment of the definition of the concept of “socio-economy”, tersely unveils that the term, “socio-economy” refers to the correlation or synergy between social and economic factors. It fundamentally entails a complex process of associating the interaction of the forces of economic production with social relations. Emphatically, socio-economy as a compound word generally pertains to human involvement in economic activities, as well as the manner of relationship among humans with regards to the distribution and consumption of economic dividends in a society. The socio-economic indicators in this context involve financial security, living condition, occupation, income, financial security, health, education, among other things.

Socio-economic development on the other hand, simply refers to the social and economic development of a society. It is typically suggestive of an institutionalised effort basically aimed at maximally improving the social and material wellbeing of the people in any given society. Socio-economic development denotes deliberate policies, schemes and strategies to improve the living standard of the people in any given politically organised society. In a more comprehensive term, socio-economic development fundamentally presupposes the deliberate exploitation, transformation and translation of the natural resources of a society into tangible social and economic benefits with the capacity to improve the living standard of the people in any given politically organised society. According to Odimgbe (2021), socio-economic development constitutes a policy initiative by the government aimed at providing essential infrastructural services to make the living condition of the people in a society comfortable and conducive. In their separate opinion, Okwuoha (2021), informed that socio-economic development denotes an institutional action which is mostly undertaken by the government to lift majority of people in any given society, region or nation from the state of poverty, misery and social discomfort, to a satisfactory level of social and economic wellbeing. In corroboration, Enang (2021) impressed that the socio-economic development of any society or state summarily represents a barest level of reduction in the rate of poverty and infrastructural misery. Also, Emodi (2024), emphasised that socio-economic development consists in the sufficient presence of social and physical infrastructural development indicators like high level of employment opportunities, living wages and allowances for workers, quality education, quality healthcare, good road network with functional drainage system, security of lives and property, among other things, to improve the living standard of the populace.

Host Communities of Oil Producing Areas in Nigeria

Nigeria’s Petroleum, which in its crude state is referred to as hydrocarbon (oil and gas) was originally discovered in commercial quantity on January 1956. The historic discovery was made in Oloibiri, a small community in Ogbia local government area of today’s Bayelsa State. The company that achieved this historic feat was the Shell D’Arcy, now known as Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC). The Oloibiri oilfield was the first oilfield in Nigeria, and indeed West Africa. For the first time in Nigeria, crude oil pipeline was laid from Oloibiri oilfield to Port Harcourt, on the Bonny River. In the year 1958, Nigeria made her first crude oil export through the Bonny export terminal, with an initial production capacity of 5,000 barrels of crude oil per day. The growth in the volume of crude oil production in Nigeria, over the years has been progressive. Currently, Nigeria can boast of over 1,386,000 barrels of crude oil per day. In 1971, Nigeria joined the Organisation of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC). In the year 1972, Nigeria was ranked the 7th crude oil producer in the world. Currently, the country is ranked the 6th in the world in terms of crude oil production. After the discovery of crude oil in Oloibiri community in Bayelsa State, other discoveries in urban and remote communities in the Niger Delta region of southern Nigeria. Subsequently, successful crude oil exploration and discoveries were recorded between 1957 and 1958 at Afam in Oyigbo local government area of Rivers State, Bomu in Gokana local government area of Rivers State, among others (Yusuf & Abejide, 2013; CEIC, 2024).

Host communities of crude oil producing areas in Nigeria, comprise the various communities or localities where oil companies situate and operate. Hence, it is by reason of the ascertained existence, through the process of exploration, of petroleum and natural gas (crude oil) deposits in the affected communities that oil companies decide to settle in such areas. Typically, the business of exploitation and production of crude oil underscore the motive for the existence of oil companies in such communities. There are nine oil-producing states in Nigeria which are often referred to as Niger-Delta states. These states include, Ondo, Edo, Delta, Bayelsa, Rivers, Imo, Abia, Akwa Ibom, and Cross River. The dominant oil producing states comprise the six states in the south-south geo-political zone and they include, Rivers state, Delta state, Edo state, Akwa Ibom state, Bayelsa state and Cross River state. Essentially, the various communities from these states constitute hosts to the many oil companies operating in Nigeria.

In the course of crude oil exploration, exploitation and production by oil companies, the host communities are usually adversely affected. Over time, these communities in the Niger-delta region of Nigeria where petroleum and natural gas are being explored in commercial quantities experience a sustained high level of environmental pollution and degradation. Such has often led to the growing incidences of lands where crop farming and other agricultural activities take place. The direct consequence of this manifests large scale food shortage and high level of hunger in the affected communities. Also, rivers, lakes, ponds and streams in most of these oil producing communities get persistently polluted by oil spillages. This experience has often led to the wanton extermination of fishes and other sea animals. The constant pollution of lakes, rivers and dams by the activities of crude oil exploration and drilling has been known to be majorly responsible for the lack of access to good and hygienic drinking water in most oil producing communities in Nigeria. Likewise, pollution of rivers and lakes caused by oil drilling activities of oil companies has been frustrating to fish farming business-the latter which is one of the major occupation of indigenes of most oil producing communities in Nigeria. Similarly, several incidences of gas flaring have been known over time, to emit very pernicious pollutants. It has severally been observed such gas flaring pollutions if inhaled could be lethal to the human body. According to Bredino et al (2022), medical studies have revealed that the inhalation of pollutions from gas emission is poisonous to human cardiovascular health and has over the years, proven to contribute to about 64% of the diseases of the lungs.

Unfortunately, in the Nigerian situation, host communities of oil companies in Nigeria are not being adequately compensated for the high degree of negative impact of petroleum exploration and exploitation. The obvious lack or paucity of essential amenities, critical for quality living is an indisputable testament to the extent of neglect of host communities of oil companies in Nigeria. In the opinion of Minima and Bredino (2018), the high level of poverty and the evidently poor living condition that characterise the socio-economic existence of the peoples of the Niger delta region in Nigeria do not justify or duly compensate for the status of the various communities in the Niger-delta as constituting the principal source of revenue for the entire country and also contributing very generously to Nigeria's foreign exchange earnings.

Aside the compelling need to compensate host communities of oil producing firms through developmental projects, based on the impact of environmental damages done to these communities in the course of crude oil production, the fact that revenues are earned through the exploitation of resources from these regions should provide a natural justification for compensation. The central objective of the Nigerian local content act of 2010 stipulates that the activities of exploration and exploitation of mineral resources should attract the provision of sustainable value to host communities from where such resources are extracted. This holistically entails that host communities of oil firms should be entitled to quality healthcare, quality education with scholarships, good and motorable road network, portable pipe-borne water, recreational facilities, enlarged employment opportunities, a sustainable process of provision of welfare packages, among other things. The deplorable socio-economic standing of oil producing communities in Nigeria has over time, not rightfully portrayed them as hosts to oil producing companies-the latter whose activities are known to generate enormous wealth. Regrettably, the profundity of wealth

generated on daily basis from the operational activities of oil companies has an infinitesimal reflection in the socio-economic status of the various communities who play host to oil firms (local and foreign).

Operational Modalities and Implementation Objectives of the Host Communities' Development Trust Under the Petroleum Industry Act, 2021.

According to Akinkugbe (2024), essentially, the basic objectives of the communities' development trust of the PIA exist in four different categories. These include:

Project Financing and Execution: This is expected to include the 3% of production budget of oil companies which the PIA mandates oil firms to allocate to their host communities. Also, financing of projects by oil companies must include the various funding of schemes under the corporate social responsibility arrangement. Apart from this, on the side of the government, special intervention funds should be coming from the coffers of the government to aid developmental projects in oil producing communities in Nigeria.

Comprehensive Approach to Infrastructural Development of Host Communities: Under the communities' development trust of the PIA, it is expected that there should be an intensive approach to infrastructural development in the communities where crude oil is produced in large commercial quantity by oil companies. Such is expected to include quality access roads (motorable with good drainage system), building of hospitals, schools, industries, skill acquisition centres, etc. Again, under the act, it is expected that this effort should be jointly undertaken by both the government and oil companies.

Enhanced Educational Development of Host Communities: In addition to building schools, the PIA, under the communities' development trust anticipates and envisages increased level of emphasis and attention given to the oil producing communities with regards to educational development. Under this arrangement, efforts should be directed towards ensuring educational growth and development in these communities in the area of increased funding. Increased funding in this context is expected to have implications for advancement in science, information technology, entrepreneurship and scholarships.

Environmental Protection Against Future Hazards: The PIA initiative also anticipates a determined collaborative effort by all stakeholders in the oil and gas industry in Nigeria, to mitigate the surge in environmental pollution of oil producing communities. The relevance of the communities' development trust in this respect should involve adequate funding aimed at cleaning or rehabilitating polluted areas of the host communities and also mechanisms or improved technologies aimed at forestalling the recurring activities of environmental pollutions and degradation.

The prospects of a successful implementation of the above stated objectives of the Petroleum Industry Act depend most on the ability to resolve the long-existing challenges in the administration of the petroleum industry. This basically concerns the supposed effective management of the responsibility of both the government and oil companies for the affairs of oil producing communities in Nigeria. Accordingly, Adeola (2023), identified some perceived administrative constraints which if not competently resolved could have the propensity to pose a serious challenge to the realisation of the core objectives of the Petroleum Industry Act of 2021 as it pertains to solving the myriad of socio-economic needs of the host communities of oil producing firms. Some of the issues according to Adeola (2023) include:

High Level of Socio-Economic Discontent in Host Communities: On account of the long-existing vulnerability of oil-producing communities in Nigeria to constant environmental degradation and low quality of life, there has been, a growing degree of dissatisfaction and disaffection among members of the host communities of oil-producing firms. Hence, such trends have often led to series of agitations, protests and recorded cases of civil unrest in the affected communities. It has been observed that several interventional efforts in the past by notable oil companies have not been potent enough to douse the unending agitations in most oil producing communities in Nigeria. Hence, according to Eferbor (2022), the enormity of socio-economic challenges in oil producing communities have continued to compound the abilities of oil companies to intervene in ameliorating the socio-economic challenges and needs of host communities. In their separate view, Akinkugbe (2024), rationalised that in most situations, high

level of socio-economic discontent in oil-producing communities in Nigeria can be attributed to the high level of political and bureaucratic corruption in our political/administrative system. Such situation arises when on the one hand, political office holders, especially in the executive arm of government display a lack of political will by not faithfully committing sufficient resources for developmental projects and the underhand dealings of civil/public servants in the course of implementation of policies, programmes and projects on the other hand. Also, Adeola (2023), observed that high level of discontent among members of host communities can be blamed on the various shades of insinuations and incitements from individuals and groups with ulterior and self-serving motives and agenda. Still on this, Agbarakwe and Bredino (2024), informed that in some situations, the activities of corrupt community leaders like traditional rulers who corner a greater chunk of socio-economic benefits meant for the development of host communities, could turn back and incite the people against either the government or oil companies. Such a situation could have the propensity to cause a high level of socio-economic discontent in oil-producing communities in Nigeria.

Poor Level of Mutual Trust between Oil Companies and their Host Communities: Over the years, on account of past incidences of failed, delayed or denied socio-economic developmental promises by oil companies to their host communities, the latter seem to exhibit a deep sense of lack of confidence in the former. This, in very many occasions usually manifests incidences like operational sabotage and hostility on the activities of oil companies. On the other hand, the oil companies, given past experiences where leaders of their host communities conspire to siphon financial and other resources meant for economic development of the oil regions, it then becomes normal that these oil companies would develop a sense of mistrust on the status of community leaders, especially traditional rulers as honest custodians of the traditions and social co-existence of the indigenes and residents of oil-producing communities. To this end, oil companies would normally drag their feet with regards to continuously committing financial resources and other welfare materials for the sustained socio-economic development of their host communities. In the circumstance therefore, such situation is viewed as posing confrontational to the realisation of the objectives of the Petroleum Industry Act as it pertains to the socio-economic development of oil-producing communities in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.

The conscious approach to socio-economic development and emancipation of oil-producing communities is pivotal to achieving and sustaining a peaceful co-existence between oil companies and their host communities. It constitutes a natural but deserving right for oil-producing communities to earn satisfactorily from the activities of crude oil exploration and exploitation which invariably generates huge revenue for oil producing firms on regular basis. Typical of the Nigerian situation reveals an ever-trending experience where the high level of socio-economic dilapidation in oil-producing communities attests to a seemingly poor administration of the developmental needs of oil-producing communities by both the government and oil companies. Often times, the various strategies and efforts institutionally initiated to ameliorate the plight of host communities of petroleum and natural oil firms have yielded inconsequential gains.

This study has unmasked the inherent prospects in the objectives of the Petroleum Industry Act, as it pertains to the socio-economic development of host communities of oil companies in Nigeria. The Petroleum Industry Act of 2021 heralds a deluge of positive and mouth-watering innovations in the oil and gas industry, with regards to holistically addressing the long-existing developmental challenges in oil-producing communities. However, the much-anticipated improvement in the socio-economic condition of oil-producing communities depends on the level of commitment, sincerity and timely execution of the various provisions of the Petroleum Industry Act. The expected resolution to the challenges currently faced by host communities of oil companies should be approached comprehensively through vigorous implementation strategies and methods. Hence, a high level of administrative transparency and accountability is required in this effort so that the core objective of ensuring that oil-

producing communities get a fair share of the benefits of the economic resource potentials naturally deposited in their immediate environments is maximally realised.

To sufficiently actualise the implementation of the objectives of the PIA 2021 with regards to host community socio-economic development, the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC), is expected to be stringent with regards to the enforcement of compliance and adherence to the various regulations and laws governing operations by oil companies. This must involve the imposition of penalties and sanctions on defaulters.

There should also be an effective and well-enhanced financial reporting system by oil companies with a view to ensuring a high level of transparency and accountability. The fundamental rationale behind this is to ensure that the financial transactional dealings of by oil companies are made open such that it will be easy to know the production costs, as well as profits and losses by oil companies. Hence, such will be needful in determining the tax status of oil companies, as well as their eligibility or otherwise of undertaking their routine corporate social responsibilities-the latter which are directed towards providing infrastructural development for their host communities.

Also, host communities should be provided with an enabling framework and legal basis to seek redress in the court of law or litigate against defaulting oil companies.

Finally, there should be institutional capacity building in the domain of the host communities such that they can become stakeholders in the utilisation of funds, earmarked for the implementation of the various economic empowerment projects meant for oil companies.

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